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The Identity of the Suffering Servant in Isaiah 53

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Isaiah

by

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Introduction

Isaiah 53 is a poetic prophecy about a servant that suffers and dies for the sins of others (Isaiah 53).¹ It is considered an important prophecy by the New Testament writers, many Church Fathers, Jewish Scholars, and modern Christian Scholars. However, there is definite disagreement over the identity of the servant. Those that are Christian tie the servant to Jesus Christ while those that are Jewish see the servant as corporate Israel or an individual from the Biblical period and beyond.² The text, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53: Encountering the Suffering Servant in Jewish and Christian Theology*, covers all these views in a series of essays. Some topics examined include the identity of the corporate Servant in Isaiah, the identity of the individual Servant in Isaiah, and the relationship between the Messiah and the Servant. Ultimately, it is not necessary to see one or the other and the song of the suffering servant can be fulfilled in Israel as a type with ultimate fulfillment taking place through Jesus Christ.

The Identity of the Corporate Servant in Isaiah

Throughout history after the prophecy was given many, mainly Jews but including Church father Origen,³ saw the suffering servant as either the whole of Israel or a righteous remnant within Israel. The belief was that Israel's past or future suffering at the hands of Gentile nations would fulfil the criteria to be the servant.⁴

¹ Unless otherwise stated, all Bible verses are sourced from *ESV: Study Bible: English Standard Version* Wheaton, IL: Crossway Bibles, 2016.

² Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53: Encountering the Suffering Servant in Jewish and Christian Theology* Grand Rapids, MI: Kregel Academic, 2012, 232.

³ *Ibid.*, 64.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 77.

This is an understandable assumption since Isaiah 40-55, sometimes called “Second Isaiah”, points to a period after Judah had been taken into Exile.⁵ Therefore, the suffering servant could be seen as the exiled people suffering at the hands of the Babylonians or the remnant within that people that stayed faithful and returned to the Promised Land instead of staying in Babylon.

It is obvious in Isaiah that Israel is the chosen people of Yahweh. Before Isaiah 53, there are several references to Israel as the chosen so an argument can be made to see Isaiah 53 as referring to a corporate Israel as the servant. In order to argue for a corporate translation, there needs to be evidence in the text itself speaks of a corporate person instead of a single individual. One potential item is that the term servant is used for corporate Israel throughout much of the book of Isaiah. This includes Isaiah 49:3 and Isaiah 54-66.⁶ There are also parts of Isaiah 53 where Jewish authorities have argued for a plural servant. One example is that verse 8 that can point to a plural servant instead of an individual.⁷ Specifically, there is disagreement over whether the one who is punished for the sins of the people is an individual servant or the people themselves.⁸

⁵ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 38.

⁶ Ibid., 93.

⁷ Ibid., 90.

⁸ Ibid., 66-72.

Verse 9 sees a couple of attempts by Jewish rabbis to show a corporate people instead of an individual. The medieval rabbi, known by the Hebrew acronym RaDak, sees verse 9 as not referring to an individual. When it is stated that the servant is buried “with the rich”, RaDak sees the killing of Jews for being rich.⁹ Another medieval rabbi, known by the Hebrew acronym Rashi, saw verse 9 as saying “in his deaths”, meaning multiple people being subjected to a manner of different deaths.¹⁰

In the final 27 books of Isaiah, servant is plural. In these chapters, Isaiah uses the word as a technical term like how modern corporations are represented as a legal person. This is common in Hebrew thought where a nation can be seen as a corporate person in much the same way as a corporation.¹¹

The Identity of the Individual Servant in Isaiah

As noted earlier, servant language in much of Isaiah is corporate, but a good argument can be made that the 4th Servant Song of Isaiah 53 speaks of an individual. Most Christians from the writers of the New Testament until modern times see the servant in Isaiah 53 as being an individual, specifically Jesus Christ. There have also been Jewish scholars that have read Isaiah 53 as referring to an individual, but in those cases it was another Biblical figure. Some options have included Moses, Ezekiel, the Persian Monarch Cyrus, and the prophet Isaiah himself.¹² Finally, it should be noted that in modern times some Jews have proposed Menachem Mendel

⁹ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 72.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 72.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 96.

¹² *Ibid.*, 94.

Schneerson, an Orthodox rabbi that passed away in 1994.¹³ While the corporate argument relied on translation, the argument for an individual is mainly based on context.

There is evidence in Isaiah 53 to assign the identity of the servant to an individual. Verses 2-4 each reference an individual. In verses four and five, the servant takes on the griefs, sorrows, and transgressions of the people. Jewish scholars attempting to make the servant Israel claim that the ones speaking here are Gentile rulers. There has even been the suggestion that Isaiah 53 didn't come from Isaiah but from a Jewish sect influenced by the Greeks and that the song was influenced by Greek tragedies.¹⁴ Brown states that if this had been the Gentile rulers, they would be the ones making Israel suffer instead of Israel suffering for them.¹⁵ It is true that Israel was created to be a nation of priests to bring the Gentile nations back to Yahweh (Exodus 19:6), however it was not stated that bringing them back involved taking on their sins and dying as a sacrifice for them.

Going back to verse 9, the servant has done no violence and "there is no deceit in his mouth". It would be very hard to make this fit Judah, as by the time of Isaiah, they had been involved in quite a bit of violence and deceit to the point of being compared to Sodom and Gomorrah (Isaiah 1:10-12). However, it can fit an individual such as Isaiah or Jesus Christ. Likewise, the people of Israel suffered a lot, but it was always because of their own sin. In contrast, the servant of Isaiah 53 suffers for the sins of the people and not by any fault of his own.

¹³ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 232.

¹⁴ Cullen Story, "Another Look at the Fourth Servant Song of Second Isaiah," *Horizons in Biblical Theology* 31, no. 2 (2009): pp. 100-110, doi:10.1163/019590809x12553238842989, 102.

¹⁵ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 77.

The writers of the New Testament also saw the servant in Isaiah 53 as an individual. This is explicitly stated in the Book of Acts when the Ethiopian Eunuch asks for the identity of the servant. Philip answers that the servant is Jesus Christ (Acts 8:34-35). It is also explicitly mentioned in Matthew which states, “This was to fulfill what had been spoken through the prophet Isaiah, He took our infirmities and bore our diseases” (Matthew 8:17). Other explicit references include Luke 22:36, and John 12:37.¹⁶

The Relationship between the Messiah and the Servant

The servant of Isaiah 53 has a clear messianic connection whether one connects him to Christ. For instance, verse 5 states that “with his wounds we are healed” (Isaiah 53:5), verse 11 states that “by his knowledge shall the righteous one, my servant, make many to be accounted righteous” (Isaiah 53:11) and verse 12 states “yet he bore the sin of many, and makes intercession for the transgressors” (Isaiah 53:12). As stated, the chapter is referenced many times in the Gospel and in each case connects the servant to Christ, the Messiah. Jesus even tied himself to the verse in the Book of Luke when he stated “For I tell you, this Scripture must be fulfilled in me, ‘And he was counted among the lawless’; and indeed, what is written about me is being fulfilled” (Luke 22:36).

As stated earlier, corporate Israel cannot completely fulfill the role of the servant in Isaiah 53 due to the requirement that the servant be a sacrifice for the sins of others. While this narrows the options down to an individual, it further limits things to the Messiah of Christianity

¹⁶ Marc Brettler and Amy-Jill Levine, “Isaiah’s Suffering Servant: Before and after Christianity,” *Interpretation: A Journal of Bible and Theology* 73, no. 2 (October 2019): pp. 158-173, doi:10.1177/0020964318820594, 10.

as the only one that could possibly fulfill the criteria.¹⁷ It is understandable that the links between Isaiah 53 and the mission of the Messiah can be tricky, almost all prophecy considering Christ's mission was somewhat obscured to prevent the forces of evil from figuring things out before His death and resurrection. In his letter to the Corinthians, Paul calls the knowledge of Christ's mission "a secret and hidden wisdom of God" and that had the rulers of the world known, "they would not have crucified the Lord of glory" (1 Corinthians 2:7-8). Paul goes on to reference Isaiah 53 in the very next verse.¹⁸

Conclusion

Isaiah 53 is a complicated song with messianic implications. There are reasons to believe that within its verses, both corporate Israel and an individual Jesus Christ are mentioned. This would suggest that in Isaiah 53, corporate Israel acts as a type that is completely fulfilled in the person of Jesus Christ. Israel was supernaturally created to be Yahweh's people and bring all other people's back to Yahweh. Their mission looked forward to Jesus who was also supernaturally birthed and who successfully provided a way through His sacrifice for all believers to find salvation and return to Yahweh. Israel was the imperfect servant of Yahweh and Christ was the servant that ultimately fulfilled the role of Israel.

¹⁷ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 94.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, 146.

It is unfortunate that most Jews are unfamiliar with Isaiah 53 as it is a fantastic tool to help them come to Christ.¹⁹ The fact that it has supernatural components and shows that Yahweh went through massive sacrifice for humanity are similarly a great tool when evangelizing to postmoderns.²⁰ As the course text has shown, Isaiah 53 is a many faceted prophecy that speaks to the mission of Christ and shows just how much He was willing to endure to be the suffering servant and bring salvation to His people.

¹⁹ Darrell L. Bock and Mitch Glaser, *The Gospel According to Isaiah 53*, 229-230.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 214.

Works Cited

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